

Importance of Information Communication in Teaching Engineering Graphics

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Abstract:

The article focuses on managing innovation activities in the higher education system using information technology. Information and communication technologies serve as an important tool for increasing the efficiency of management and training. It has been suggested that intensive implementation of the process will lead to positive changes in the education system.

Keywords: Education, innovation, innovative technologies, information and communication technologies, informatization, hypothesis, information transmission system.

INTRODUCTION

By introducing innovative technologies into the educational process, the teacher will have to prepare himself for the newly created conditions. Relying on new technologies, rich experiences gathered in our republic, combining them with innovative technologies, it is necessary to work together scientifically and methodically to create our own modern pedagogical technology. It is necessary to create a system of "Innovative schools" on the basis of our own modern innovative pedagogical technologies.

Information and communication technologies are used in the teaching of all subjects in such schools. Then the "teacher-computer-student" system will be created instead of "teacher-teacher". Well, let's dwell on the question of what innovation is.

Main part: Innovation (English) means innovation, innovation, change. This phrase is mainly associated with science and technology. However, it is becoming popular that innovation is widely used in activities related to human life, mainly in the process of pedagogic education, and great progress is being made in education and training using new technologies.

Innovation is the introduction of innovations in technology, technologies, achievements of science and the implementation of advanced experiences, increasing the quality and effect of education in the educational system, introducing new pedagogical technologies into the educational process.

Innovative technologies are methods and means of implementing innovations. The process of reconstruction of pedagogical technologies by updating existing ideas and hypotheses.

It is necessary to understand the innovative approach to the educational process, to develop students' desire to acquire new experiences, to cultivate creativity and critical thinking, and to cultivate a desire for the future.

Technology - Greek "techne" - art, "logos" - study (knowledge, education). Technology in a broad sense - the volume of knowledge, in a narrow sense - methods of restructuring (radically changing) existence.

In the history of mankind, it is believed that man first created the technology of friction to get fire, to transport heavy load from one place to another using wheels. As a result of the rise of development, the modern way of life has been reached thanks to such simple technologies.

Technologies can be classified into innovative technologies, engineering technologies, information technologies, telecommunication technologies.

Initially, the term Information and Communication Technologies is clustered.

The current stage of society's development is directly characterized by the improvement of technologies. Modern technological processes are affecting every industry. Especially in the information transmission system, new technologies of change are gaining strength. The use of information and communication technologies and computer technology is developing.

Their use in the field of education of our republic has become an urgent issue of our time to increase the quality of teaching, to increase and expand the scope of thinking of students, and to strengthen their independent learning activities.

Along with students' assimilation of information and communication technologies in the informatization of education, it leads to the acceleration of their knowledge and skills in the field of science. These processes lead to different methodological approaches as a result of scientific research.

Distance networking courses and competitions are becoming more popular day by day. The teacher is no longer the only center that delivers knowledge, but is becoming a provider and receiver of distance education with the use of technology.

The advent and development of the Internet is due to the development of computer technology, not telephone or television. Today, the development in this field is much ahead of the development in other fields and the pace is fast.

History of the Internet (briefly) On October 29, 1969, the first attempt was made to remotely connect two computers, a computer at the Stanford Research Center (SRI) to a computer at the University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA). Although this effort was unsuccessful, the attempt to connect two computers at a distance of 500 km was the first attempt to create the Internet, and these two computers were one of the future nodes of the ARPANet network.

The first tests of ARPANet were carried out in the fall of 1969. Later, two more universities, the University of California at Santa Barbara (USCB) and the University of Utah (UTAH), joined the

network, and it was these four institutions that jointly developed the first Wide Area Network, that is, network computers that span large distances divided their tasks:

- ✓ University of Los Angeles - conducting measurement tests;
- ✓ Stanford University - creating an information center;
- ✓ Santa Barbara University - development of mathematical apparatus;
- ✓ University of Utah - First work on three-dimensional graphics.

On September 1, 1969, the BBN company had the opportunity to conduct tests in exchange for the creation of the first copies of the IMP (Interface Message Professor) device, which provides communication between computer and telephone channels.

The current name of the Internet was proposed in 1974 by Vint Cerf and Bob Kahn in their article on the TCP protocol.

October 29, 1969 is tentatively recognized as the birthday of the Internet. The existence of a sequence of thousands of discoveries that prepared the ground and contributed to its creation, the creation of the "Salamin boards" (named after the island of Salamin in the Aegean Sea) in the 5th - 4th centuries BC, gave rise to considerable ease and convenience in computing, he said. Calculation operations were carried out by pushing counting bones or stones (calculator) in special grooves of the board. A similar shape of sticks has been polished and used until now.

In the first half of the 9th century, al-Khwarazmi developed decimal counting systems and created easy and convenient ways of implementing these numbers. Since he was the first to solve the problem using equations based on fixed rules, the term algorithm was introduced to the science based on his name. , discovered the perfect variant. Based on this method, a logarithmic ruler appeared 600 years later. In 1390, metal type that could be moved to publish books was discovered in Korea. In 1643, the young French mathematician and physicist Blaise Pascal performed arithmetic operations. created the car. This is the first model of an electronic calculating machine.

In 1820, K. Thomas invented the arithmetic machine.

In 1823, Charles Babbage proposed a program-controlled automatic machine, and in 1833, he proposed the scheme of the Analytical Machine.

In the 1830s and 1840s, Samuel Morse discovered telegraph communication methods (Morse code) in America.

1867 KL Schultz invented the first practical typewriter in America
did

1880 VT Odner Arithmometer with different number of teeth in Russia
invents.

In 1930, USA and USSR founded television in Tashkent as a result of Olympic research.

In 1945-1960, control works on interaction between machine and man, the first time-sharing mode was implemented, interactive tools and computing machines appeared. The current Internet is the fruit of globalization and is a huge space that is making it an unmanageable process.

The last 20th century was called the era of industrial revolution in the field of science and technology. The 21st century entered history as the information age. Today, information communities are being organized according to the spirit of the times. In particular, great work is being done on the issue of "convergence" combining independently developing technologies, loss paths between telephone, television and computer. Examples of these are the Internet and mobile phones.

History shows that it took 40 years for radio to attract a mass audience. Television achieved this in 14 years. It took only 4 years for the Internet system to attract a global audience. Therefore, today the Internet includes not only the press, but also the possibilities of radio and television.

The system of information and communication technologies includes: didactic approach to information technologies, information-pedagogical technologies, training in drawing classes in distance education.

We are witnessing the rapid development of information technologies, opening up new opportunities and the need for a new approach to the educational process in educational institutions.

There are a number of didactic possibilities of information technologies in the educational process. According to the needs of our time, information technology educational institutions can be considered as a systematizing, connecting, practical organizational factor of the educational process. Information technologies allow to compile information such as libraries, documents and creative works of students, to create a database, to systematize the educational process, to organize practical creative works of students. All these tools allow students to implement the practical skills and competencies formed in the lesson under the supervision of the teacher. The Internet allows students to quickly familiarize themselves with the work of the educational institution and post their thoughts. Assignments can be distributed via the Internet and received from local e-mail. Such assignments help to model network forms of distance learning in the classroom.

Distance networking courses and competitions are becoming more popular day by day. The teacher is no longer the only center that delivers knowledge, but with the use of computer technology, it is becoming possible to give and receive distance education. Students are often interested in self-education through the Internet, communicate with their peers, find common interests. It is becoming a means to feel opportunities, meet peers from other countries and work together.

Information technology tools allow the student to express his imagination in an "electronic form" and check the competitiveness of his product and the popularity of his ideas. In order to create a truly interesting and unique resource for a student, he must first of all study all the information, feel the characteristics of the mentality of its requirements, determine the novelty of the resource and realize its practical importance. All this is related to the formation of the student's own knowledge, skills to determine his practical direction in life.

CONCLUSION

The demand for highly qualified and mature personnel is increasing in the current period when science, technology and technology are developing. This, in turn, imposes a responsible task not only on school, vocational college teachers, but also on professors and teachers of higher education institutions. In the system of these tasks, education aimed at obtaining independent knowledge is one of the most important issues. After all, it is important to develop the ability to acquire knowledge independently, without the help of a teacher, without teaching this or that knowledge to a student.

It is known that about 25% of students learn the lecture. Experiments show that simultaneously listening to a lecture and viewing the material on a computer screen and actively controlling its display increases the quality of learning. Now multimedia educational programs are used from the composition of powerful software products such as Mat CAD, Puls 6.0. Today, there are not enough programs that use multimedia technologies. The main problem is the lack of organization of cooperation of professors and teachers with programmers who are familiar with multimedia possibilities. Such educational programs should be developed and widely distributed in drawing classes.

The basic meaning of the term multimedia means multiple environments. However, the exact definition of the concept of "multimedia" is not known. Usually, multimedia means a set of data

processing tools in various forms. At the same time, these are primarily tools that process sounds and video elements. At the same time, it is possible to talk about multimedia in the case of multiplication (animation) and high-quality graphics. In the future, it is possible that multimedia tools will allow working with other types of information, for example, virtual reality.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that in the process of drawing classes, electronic lesson plans built on multimedia principles, animated graphic images, reference books, encyclopedias, translations and dictionaries were effectively used in history, geography, medicine, sports and other fields. Therefore, it is necessary to develop electronic lesson plans, animated graphic images, reference books, encyclopedias and dictionaries for engineering graphics subjects.

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